

Underwater acoustic communication based on noise similar chaotic modulated signals

Luka Lazović

University of Montenegro
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Podgorica, Montenegro
lukal@ucg.ac.me

Jeffrey Neasham

School of Engineering
Newcastle University
Newcastle, United Kingdom
jeff.neasham@newcastle.ac.uk

Benjamin Sherlock

School of Engineering
Newcastle University
Newcastle, United Kingdom
benjamin.sherlock@newcastle.ac.uk

Ana Jovanović

University of Montenegro
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Podgorica, Montenegro
anaj@ucg.ac.me

Vesna Rubežić

University of Montenegro
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Podgorica, Montenegro
vesnar@ucg.ac.me

Abstract— This paper presents a proposal for a new chaotic-based underwater acoustic modulation scheme. The proposed method is a differential chaotic shift keying modulation based on the Lorenz attractor. Unlike conventional techniques that use Chirp signals, synchronization is achieved using a chaotic signal. In the demodulator, a Doppler shift compensator is also implemented, capable of compensating shifts up to 10 m/s. This compensator is based on bank of Doppler shifts. In order to see the influence of underwater acoustic channel on the proposed acoustic signal, the simulations are performed. The channel was modeled by adding white Gaussian noise with a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) ranging from -5 dB to 20 dB, multipath propagation with 7 received waves, and the Doppler effect with a speed of ± 10 m/s.

The experimental verification of the proposed waveform was conducted in an anechoic tank at the SEA Laboratory at the University of Newcastle, as well as during sea trials in Kumbor, Montenegro. The experiments tested the influence of high impulsive noise generated by crustaceans and the presence of high noise generated by vessels. Simulation results and experimental verification demonstrated that the proposed modulation technique is resistant to underwater noise, both Gaussian and impulsive, and is suitable for operation in complex channels with significant multipath fading and attenuation. Furthermore, it offers the advantage of being environmentally friendly.

Keywords—Chaotic modulation, Underwater acoustic communication, Doppler shift

I. INTRODUCTION

With the accelerated development of underwater robotics and the IoT concept, underwater acoustic communications are becoming a dominant factor in research circles [1]. They find extensive and diverse applications in oceanographic research, underwater exploration, environmental monitoring, underwater surveillance, and offshore industry operations. Acoustic communications involve long-distance communication between submerged devices such as submarines, underwater sensors, or remotely operated vehicles (ROVs). Acoustic communications represent the only way for long-distance communication underwater because light cannot spread in turbid water and EM waves have a large attenuation due to the conductivity of water. However, these communications have not received significant attention from researchers. The drawbacks of acoustic communications compared to electromagnetic (EM) communications are mainly due to the very slow speed of sound, leading to pronounced Doppler shift and low data rates [2]. With the increasing need for underwater communications,

there is a growing demand for improving these communications on one hand and implementing underwater acoustic networks on the other.

Researchers face a significant technical challenge in increasing the security of data transmission, improving data rates, and enhancing resistance to noise in underwater communication [3][2]. Their efforts are mainly focused on improving modulation techniques and attempting to implement some well-known techniques used in electromagnetic (EM) communications. However, in terms of environmental protection, it cannot be said that the existing techniques are environmentally friendly because they have a negative impact on marine life. The environmental community has been increasingly insisting on reducing the level of underwater noise pollution, which is impossible to achieve with current techniques.

One way to overcome these problems is to design environmentally friendly acoustic communications based on chaotic signals. Namely, chaotic signals are said to be noise-similar signals, so the sound generated in this way would not differ from the usual noise that is present under water. Therefore, it would not have any effect on the living world under water.

The challenges in designing a new modulation scheme based on chaos include the method and algorithm for addressing synchronization issues, multipath propagation, and Doppler shift while also being environmentally friendly.

Acoustic communications are not inherently secure; information packets can be easily detected and intercepted. Chaotic modulation could make a significant contribution to the development of secure communications, as chaotic signals are difficult to decode [4]. This is of particular importance for offshore industry operations. The complex and non-repetitive nature of chaotic signals and random-like behavior makes it difficult for unauthorized users to intercept and decipher the transmitted information.

II. CHAOTIC MODULATION

A. Chaos theory

Chaos theory describes the behavior of certain dynamic systems that are highly sensitive to initial conditions. Chaos manifests in many natural and man-made systems [5]. The waveforms of chaotic signals differ from periodic waveforms, appearing irregular and random, with no repetition over time. The spectrum of chaotic signals is noise-similar, making them very favorable for use in enhancing the security of acoustic

communications where signal masking is required. On the other hand, this makes them environmentally friendly [6].

In this paper, chaotic modulation utilized the Lorenz attractor, which is described by the following differential equations [5], [6], [9]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= \sigma(y - x) \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= x(\rho - z) - y, \\ \frac{dz}{dt} &= xy - \beta z \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

where σ , ρ , and β are constants. In the simulations, the values $\sigma = 10$, $\rho = 28$, and $\beta = 8/3$ were used.

The time-domain signal shape generated by these differential equations and used in the proposed chaotic modulation is shown in the Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Chaotic signal waveform generated by equation 1.1 used in proposed modulation

B. Differential chaotic shift keying (DCSK)

As mentioned earlier, one of the major challenges when using chaotic signals in communications is the synchronization of the receiver and transmitter. Considering the requirements for cost-effectiveness in this communication system, it is often best and simplest to use non-coherent modulation, specifically differential chaotic shift keying modulation. The advantage of this modulation, especially in the case of long-duration acoustic communications (due to the relatively low speed of sound), is its insensitivity to frequency-selective and time-variant channels [7]. This type of modulation does not require synchronization between the modulator and demodulator [8][9].

The block diagram of the modulator and demodulator is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of DCSK modulator and demodulator

The principle of DCSK modulation is as follows: the reference signal is sent in the first half of the symbol period, and the signal carrying the message in the second half. If a "1" is

to be sent, the data signal will be identical to the reference signal. If a "-1" is to be sent, the inverted version of the reference signal will be used as the data-carrying signal. During demodulation, the received signal is correlated with the same signal but only delayed by half a period, which is essentially a correlation of the reference signal and the data-carrying signal. After correlation, a decision is made, and all values that exceed zero are set to "1," while the rest are set to "0."

One of the drawbacks of DCSK modulation is that it reduces the transmission rate since the reference signal is transmitted during half of the transmission time.

C. Doppler Compensation algorithm and synchronization

Due to the significantly lower speed of sound compared to electromagnetic waves, acoustic communications are highly susceptible to the Doppler effect, which is not as prominent in standard EM communications. Moreover, in underwater communications, there are both horizontal and vertical movements of transmitters and receivers due to ocean currents, waves, and vessel motion. The conventional approach to address the Doppler effect and packet synchronization involves adding Chirp signals at the beginning and end of the message since Chirp signals are Doppler-resistant [10][11][12].

However, the concept of this research is to generate a signal that cannot be easily decoded and is similar characteristics to other underwater acoustic noises [3]. For packet synchronization, a chaotic signal is used. This synchronization packet is known to both the transmitter and the receiver (as chaotic signals are deterministic, knowing the initial conditions and the duration of the synchronization packet is sufficient)

Autocorrelation on the receiving end can easily detect the beginning of a packet, facilitating decoding. In the case of the Doppler effect, a Chirp signal could be used at the start and end of the data packet. The receiver could then estimate the time between the first and second Chirp signals and use this information to estimate and correct the Doppler shift. In this case, the only option is to employ a Doppler shift bank on the receiving side. This bank contains resampled sequences for synchronization within a certain range of Doppler shifts (in this case, it can compensate for Doppler shifts for speed ± 10 m/s). The maximum value of the cross-correlation will indicate the Doppler shift. The block diagram for the receiver structure for Doppler compensation is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Receiver block structure for Doppler compensation

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation of the entire system has been created in MATLAB. In the proposed system, textual data is transmitted (68 bits total). To facilitate error detection and correction, a Convolutional coder and Viterbi decoder have been

implemented. The time-domain signal waveform and spectrogram are shown in Figure 4 and 5 respectively.

Fig. 4. Chaotic modulated waveform

Fig. 5. Spectrogram of Chaotic modulated waveform from Figure 4

The influence of the underwater acoustic channel on the proposed acoustic signal was simulated. The channel was modeled by adding white Gaussian noise with a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) ranging from -5 dB to 20 dB, multipath propagation with 7 received waves, and the Doppler effect with a speed of ± 10 m/s. In all simulations, the decoder successfully decoded the transmitted message.

The simulated BER (Bit Error Rate) is shown on Figure 6. Decoding can be successfully achieved for SNR values above -5 dB.

Fig. 6. Simulated BER

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For the purpose of verifying the simulation results, experiments were conducted in an anechoic tank at the SEA

Laboratory at Newcastle University and in the sea at Kumbor, Montenegro.

A. Anechoic tank experiment

The measurement setup for the experiment in the anechoic tank consisted of a laptop playing audio, a power amplifier, and a transducer on the transmitter side. On the receiver side, there was a laptop recording audio, a bandpass filter, an amplifier, and a hydrophone. To analyze the impact of acoustic signal attenuation, the amplifier gain on the receiver side was varied from 0 dB to 30 dB. Due to the equipment's operating frequency, the central frequency of this signal was 12 kHz. In all cases, the decoded message was retrieved without error correction during transmission using the Viterbi decoder. Spectrograms in these two cases are shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Spectrogram of Chaotic modulated waveform for gain 30dB and gain 0dB respectively

B. Sea trials in Kumbor

To investigate the behavior and characteristics of the proposed waveform in real-world conditions, an experiment was conducted at the location in Kumbor, Montenegro (Figure 8). The spectrogram shown in the figure represents the recorded signal between two positions on the dock, which are 10 meters apart. The transducers were placed very close to the dock. The reason for this experimental setup was the presence of significant impulsive noise, referred to as "clicks," produced by various crustacean species in this area. Figure 9 shows the recorded signal in time domain.

Fig. 8. Experiment location aerial view

For acoustic communications, these "clicks" represent a worst-case scenario, making this a unique opportunity to test communication reliability. In the Figure 9, the impulsive noises from these clicks are vertical lines. During the experiment, maritime traffic was also significant, adding to

the complexity of the acoustic environment. Figure 10 shows the channel impulse response.

Fig. 9. Spectrogram of Chaotic signal recorded in experiment in Kumbor

Fig. 10. Channel impulse response

The measurement setup for the sea trial consisted of a laptop playing audio with an external sound card on the transmitter side and a laptop recording audio with a transducer on the receiving side. The central frequency of this signal was 28 kHz due to the equipment used. It's worth noting that during the experiment, neither output nor input signal amplifiers were used, so the sound level was relatively weak.

The decoding results are promising, with messages successfully decoded. The error detection algorithm detected a 3-bit error (in 68 bit package), which was also successfully corrected. Based on these results, we can conclude that the proposed acoustic communication system has demonstrated success in a highly noisy environment and with a low level of emitted signal.

The experimental results showed the great success of the proposed modulation techniques, which justified the idea that the chaotic signal can be used in underwater acoustic communications.

V. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper is to present experimental results of a new proposed method for underwater acoustic communication based on chaotic DCSK modulation. The proposed differential chaotic shift modulation utilizes chaotic signals generated using the Lorenz differential equations. In addition to this modulation, the transmitter and receiver are equipped with a convolutional coder and Viterbi decoder for error detection and correction, as well as an algorithm for

Doppler shift compensation. Unlike conventional methods that use Chirp signals for synchronization, packet synchronization is achieved by adding a chaotic signal. The goal of this research is to design a modulation technique that is noise-similar. An algorithm for Doppler shift compensation has been implemented, capable of compensating shifts up to 10 m/s, based on a bank of resampled synchronization signals where the Doppler shift is determined by the one with maximum cross-correlation.

The simulation results of the proposed DCSK modulation show that the message can be decoded for various levels of white Gaussian noise with a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) ranging from -5 dB to 20 dB, multipath propagation with 7 received waves, and the Doppler effect with a speed of ± 10 m/s.

During the testing of the signal in real-world conditions, there was high impulsive noise generated by crustaceans and a significant amount of noise generated by vessels. It's important to note that signal amplifiers were not used on the transmitter and receiver in this case. The experimental results show that the message can be successfully decoded even under such challenging channel conditions. It can be concluded that the use of this modulation type for underwater acoustic communications is entirely justified.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was funded by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101060395, Twinning project MONUSEN.

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